

A STRATEGIC INTERVENTION PROGRAM AND PERFORMANCE OF GRADE IV STRUGGLING LEARNERS IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

YVETTE M. TAMARGO

kervet47@gmail.com

0000-0003-3727-5959

Lusacan Elementary School, Tiaong, Quezon, Philippines

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

With this new normal in education, most of the students struggle more than they are in school. As a response, this study aimed to determine the relationship of Strategic Intervention Program and Performance of Grade IV Struggling Learners in Public Elementary School. Specifically, it revealed the answers on the following; the respondents' profile, pretest and posttest scores of the learners in English and Mathematics, learners evaluation on strategic intervention program materials as to components and characteristics, the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in English and Mathematics of the pupils exposed to SIP materials, and lastly, the significant relationship between the evaluation of the respondents to Strategic Intervention Program materials in terms of components and characteristics and their performance in English and Mathematics. Descriptive- Correlational design and developmental in nature was used and the Grade IV struggling learners were the respondents, chosen through purposive and convenient sampling technique with questionnaire, pretest and posttest SIP materials as main tool. The study used mean and standard deviation, percentage frequency, paired t-test and Pearson Product Moment of Correlation for the significant relationship of the IV and DV. The respondents' profile, pretest and posttest scores of the learners in English and Mathematics shows a significant difference, learners evaluated the strategic intervention program materials as to components as well structured and characteristics as evident, there is significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in English and Mathematics of the pupils exposed to SIP materials and lastly, there is no significant relationship between the performance of the struggling learners and their evaluation to Strategic Intervention Program materials in terms of components and characteristics. Thus, this study recommends the use of a SIP materials in English and Mathematics to improve the performance the students.

Keywords: Strategic Intervention Program, Struggling Learners